

The Role of Tribal Disunity in the Division of the Kingdom of Ancient Israel: A Lesson for Nigeria

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Abstract

It is not an overstatement to say that the Nigeria society is characterized by regional, ethnical, religious and political segregation which to a large extent has created a lacuna in the quest for national integration and peaceful co-existence. It is pertinent to assert that since Nigeria's independence, her political structure has been built along regional sentiment and tribal chauvinism. Major political offices are being dominated by a particular geo-political zone at the detriment of others. The national income is being shared by a particular class of people all in the name of "cabals." This has however, led to serious agitations and intensive demand for secession by some ethnic groups from the Federal Republic of Nigeria. On the other hand, some ethnic groups are demanding for political re-structuring in order to balance up the polity. The focus of this paper is to examine the role of tribal cleavages in the division of the kingdom of ancient Israel and to draw out the lessons for contemporary Nigeria state. The study adopts historical, exegetical and analytical research methodologies. The findings reveal that ethnicity and tribal disunity are major factors militating against Nigeria's unity and peaceful coexistence and as such, Nigerians should learn from the devastating effects of the division of the ancient kingdom of Israel.

Keywords: Tribal disunity, Ethnicity, National integration, Peaceful co-existence, Division of the kingdom of Ancient Israel

Introduction

The clarion call for national integration has been the major concern of all sundry especially in a tensed and deteriorating situation of Nigeria today. Since independence, and most especially in recent times, the country has been threatened, troubled and divided as never before. There are numerous cases of terrorism, banditry, kidnapping, abductions and so on, which have grossly constituted a great challenge to her national security. The government of the day seems helpless in the situation, considering the various attempts at national integration and unity. The gap between the various ethnic groups seems wider as the nation is still plagued with ethnic rivalry, religious intolerance, and political exclusion, quest for self-determination, power sharing and violent agitations.¹

Omisore, Babatunde² asserts that since the arbitrary amalgamation of the Northern and Southern protectorates by Lord Lugard in 1914, the country has been battling with agents of disunity. In order to address the challenges to unity, successive governments in Nigeria (Civilian or Military) have put in place pro-unity measures such as national policy on education, National Youth Service Corps (NYSC) scheme, unity schools, national symbols, National Orientation Agency (NOA). Mantras such as "the unity of the nation is not negotiable" among others have been adopted to facilitate national unity in Nigeria. Despite all these efforts, Nigeria is still battling with the problem of disunity. The situation is not peculiar to Nigeria. The ancient kingdom of Israel that was made up of the Northern and Southern Kingdoms was somehow united during the reigns of David and Solomon. Unfortunately, after the death of Solomon, the kingdom of Israel suffered a setback and the United Kingdom split in the reign of Rehoboam the son of Solomon. This paper therefore examines the events

that led to the division of the kingdom of ancient Israel with a view to borrow a leaf from the biblical account to correct the Nigeria situation.

The Concept of National Unity

The concept of national unity is often used interchangeably with national integration, united nationality, loyalty, united community, nation building and building national identity³. According to Eme-Uche, Chukwu⁴ “National unity portends a feeling of common purpose that bind, peoples of diverse cultures, colours and ethnic nationalities together as one”. Duverger, Peter⁵ defines national unity as the process of unifying the various segments of a society to make it equitably harmonious. Also, Ojo, Bolaji⁶ describes national unity as a relationship of people within the same political entity. He further explains that it is a state of mind or disposition in which members of a community or state act together, live together and be committed to mutual goals.

The concept of national unity is also used to describe the process of uniting people of various races with different culture under one form of national identity⁷. However, the term national unity is a normative concept that may carry different meanings to different people. It can be simply defined as a state in which all citizens from various groups live in peace as one united nation, giving full commitment to national identity based upon the federal constitution. Hasan, Abdul opines that national unity is a social situation wherein the citizens consisting of diverse ethnic groups, religious beliefs and regions co-exist peacefully as one united nation⁸. In view of the above, national unity entails co-operation, co-existence among different ethnic groups, religious beliefs, in order to form a common identity for the purpose of national development. In the context of Nigeria, national unity is the synthesis of various ethnic groups into a political entity in order to foster growth and development in all areas of her national life.

Challenges to National Unity in Nigeria

Nigeria as a country is a multi-ethnic, religious and cultural entity. The three dominant ethnic groups are the Yorubas, Hausas and Igbos. According to statistics Nigeria has over 250 ethnic groups and about 500 languages with English being the official language.⁹ However, the amalgamation of the two protectorates of Nigeria in 1914 remains one of the most controversial events in Nigerian history. Adeyemi Olajide¹⁰ shares this view when he opines that “Given the ethno-religious diversity of the various groups that presently constitute modern Nigeria, the amalgamation of the southern and northern Nigeria protectorates by British colonizers in 1914 is a mistake of colonial administration.” Akinjide Richard¹¹ also opines that what the British amalgamated in 1914 was fundamentally the administration of the North and South, and not the people of the North and south.

The political structure produced by the amalgamation in 1914 sowed the seed of discord in the polity of Nigeria. There was uneven development amongst the various nationalities, especially at the level of education and the distribution of the common wealth. Hence, the Nigerian state given its origin and nature has never been conducive for democracy. This is because, it was a state created by force, dominion and imposition, rather than consensus.¹² The Luggard system of indirect rule not only compartmentalized the diverse nationalities and ethnic groups (divide and rule tactics), but also provoke crisis amongst the different ethnic groups. It can therefore be concluded that the colonial administration laid a faulty foundation for unity in Nigeria.

Ethnic Conflicts since Independence

In the post independent period, Nigeria witnessed a political scenario that was marred by ethnic politics. Political parties were structured along ethnic line. Thus, the struggle for nation hood was reduced to the quest for ethnic dominance, politicized ethnicity, coupled with competition for resource control. This however worsened the relationship amongst ethnic groups. There was also a high degree of corruption, nepotism and tribalism. Political elites from each region schemed to attract as many federal resources to their regions, neglecting issues that could have unified the country. This position is corroborated by Uwaife Osifor when he

asserts: “The composition of the Nigerian state to a large extent has contributed to the degree of underdevelopment and improper integration of the different ethnic grouping in the nation.”¹³ This resentment is reflected in the political relationship among them. It is driven by contempt, rivalry, suspicion and hatred and lingering fear of domination by the majority groups in the nation.”¹⁴ It should be stated here that the anarchy, competition and insecurity led to the demise of the first republic.

Ethnocentrism and corruption of the electoral and political process in the first republic led to the first military coup in January 15th 1966 when a collection of young soldiers from the eastern region led a coup which brought about the death of some notable politicians from the north; such as; the former prime minister, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa, Premier of Northern Region Ahmadu Bello and the Premier of Western Region Ladoke Akintola. A counter coup was carried out by soldiers of the northern extraction in July 29th of the same year which led to the death of the then Head of State General Aguiyi Ironsi (an Easterner), and other officers, paving the way for Lt. Colonel Yakubu Gowon to become the head of state. These coups led to an increase in ethnic tension and violence. It became obvious that they were carried out of tribal sentiment. The violence against the Easterners (Igbo) led to their desire and quest for their own autonomy which gave birth to the ‘Republic of Biafra’ in May 1967 (the agitation still persist till date). The declaration of the Republic of Biafra led to the Nigeria Civil war between 1967-1970, where a large number of people lost their lives.¹⁵

Going through the political history of Nigeria since independent, one can rightly deduce that the issue of ethnical differences played a major role in the disunity of Nigeria. From the first Republic to the fourth republic, the country is battling with the ‘war of ethnicity’. Political leaders are capitalizing on the ethnical segregations to achieve their selfish political gains, each geo-political zone is fighting towards political relevance without putting into cognizance national interest.

Division of the Kingdom of Israel

At this juncture, the researchers will examine the political history of Israel from the institution of monarchy to the division of the kingdom of Israel. This will take us through the reigns of Saul, David, Solomon respectively to ascertain how tribal disunity led to the division of the kingdom. Saul was the first king of Israel. He was not a king in the real sense of the term. He was a prince (1Samuel 10:1 ESV). Although, there are two traditions regarding his ascension to power; the pro-monarchy tradition (1Sam. 9:10:1-16 & 11: 1-16) and the anti-monarch tradition (I Sam 8:10:17-27& 12). The first tradition was in support of his kingship while the second was against his kingship. However, both traditions point to the fact that Saul who was the pioneer king of Israel but operated within the scope of tribal confederacy, unlike David and Solomon, he made no attempt to transform the tribal structure into a centralized state. In the words of Anderson Bernard¹⁶, “he had no oriental despot, he perpetuated the tribal democracy of the earlier period and claimed authority among the tribes, only because of his charisma. The biblical narratives painted him a failure, which may partly be due to the interest of the Deuteronomist historian who seems to favour Judah. (David Circle). However, one could still observe some tribal elements taking its share in Saul’s regime. Saul was from the tribe of Benjamin and his major opponents Samuel (representing the old tradition) and David were from the tribes of Ephraim and Judah respectively. Saul struggled throughout his reign to stabilize Israel but failed because he could not unite the tribes of Israel. At the time of his death, he left behind a country in crisis. The kingdom was still divided along tribal line, which came to limelight at the period of David.

When David became king, the kingship was transferred from the tribe of Benjamin to that of Judah. There was no reason for all the tribes to accept David as king immediately as kingship was still foreign to Israel and more so, the tribal disunity was still in place.¹⁷ The people of the Northern Kingdom were in support of Saul’s son as successor to the throne while those from the Southern kingdom were in support of David. David faced opposition from the leader of Saul’s army Abner (1Sam 17: 20). Abner supported Ishbosheth, the son of Saul and made him king for two years (2Samuel2:10). David was first proclaimed king at Hebron for seven years

where he ruled over a limited kingdom. Other tribes such as Gilead, Ephraim and Benjamin as well as the people of Jezreel were in support of Ishbosheth (II Sam. 2:8-10).

It was only after the assassination of Ishbosheth (2 Sam 4:7) that David gained control over all Israel (2Sam 5:1-3). David aimed at consolidating his position by appointing Joab, his faithful friend as commander-in-chief of his army. He also married Abigail the daughter of Saul and entered into a covenant relationship with Jonathan (Saul's son). In a bid to unite the kingdom of Israel, he established a capital in Jerusalem and brought the ark of the Lord to the city. So, Jerusalem became the political and religious capital of Israel. Despite attempts by David to unite the kingdom of Israel, there were several internal and tribal crises that ensued in his reign. His son Absalom led a revolution that almost dethroned David. Also, among the northern tribes a certain man named Sheba sounded the call to revolution: "We have no portion in David, and we have no inheritance in the son of Jesse, every man to his tents, O Israel" (2 Sam. 20:1-2). The above passage aptly shows the extent of tribal disunity in the reign of David.

The reign of Solomon was undoubtedly the Golden Age of Israel. He was able to fortified the key cities of Israel (1Kin. 9:15-19) by stationing a standing army at strategic locations. He also had a much larger court than David as he appointed 12 districts officers (1Kings 4). He developed alliances with nations like Egypt, Tyre among others and also embarked on building projects such as erecting a palace and a magnificent temple that was completed in 960 B.C. He also concentrated heavily on literary and philosophical pursuits which made him a renowned writer and composer. However, a critical look at reign of Solomon reveals that his reign was characterized by tribal jealousy. Even before his death, the tribal disunity in Israel was evident. For instance, when Solomon formed his 12 districts for the purpose of taxation, he did not include Judah (1Kin. 4). Judah apparently had a tax-free status.¹⁸ Most of the district appointees were also Judahites or pro-Judahites (1Kin. 4:11-16). Furthermore, Solomon's building projects were concentrated in Judah (the temple, the palace, the Millo and the wall of Jerusalem, the copper mines etc. whereas, most of the taxes and forced labourers came from the northern tribes. This tribal segregation on the part of Solomon led to disunity among the tribes of Israel. This position is corroborated by Wayne¹⁹ when he agreed that the jealousy among the tribes may have been the actual root cause of the division of the kingdom. The tribal disunity in the reign of Solomon was also apparent when Jeroboam from the tribe of Ephraim (in the northern part of Israel), the director of Solomon's forced labour rebelled against him for selling Galilean cities to pay for his building projects at Jerusalem. This can be interpreted to mean that Solomon stripped the north to cloth the south. Halpern²⁰ shared this view when he averred that Solomon's lavish expenditures on construction projects and the sale of northern land to fortify the south was responsible for Jeroboam's coup.

Solomon's exploitative policies have a major role to play in the division of the kingdom of Israel. He conscripted his citizens to heavy taxation and forced labour due to his elaborate projects such as building projects, military fortifications ship construction and foreign trades. For example, 30,000 men were forced into hard labour (1King. 5:13-14). David Ben Gurion lays most of the blame for the division of the kingdom on Solomon when he affirms that during the latter years of Solomon, he adopted an increasingly oppressive policy.²¹ He introduced foreign trade and increased the national income to a great extent but his wisdom failed him in his last days when his hand grew heavy upon his people. 1,400 chariots, 12,000 horsemen, and considerable infantry were a burdensome yoke in his days. On the part of God, Solomon's reign was coloured with apostasy. His marriages with foreign wives for the sake of foreign alliances was condemnable before Yahweh. According to the scriptures "his wives turned his heart away after other gods" (1Kin. 11:4). For this sole reason, God decided to tear the kingdom from him and give it to his servant (1Kin. 11:9-12).

After the death of Solomon, his son Rehoboam took over the mantle of leadership of the southern tribes (I Kin. 11:43). The Northern tribes felt they were not properly treated by Solomon. Rehoboam, realizing the need for Northern Support, seeks for special approval and confirmation from them to become the king of the United Kingdom. The northern kingdom sent representatives led by Jeroboam to Rehoboam at Shechem requesting him to reduce the heavy yoke placed on them by Solomon (I Kin. 12:4). The Old advisors who were experienced and

had stood by Solomon advised Rehoboam to accept the request of Jeroboam and the elders and reduce taxation. Instead, Rehoboam took the counsel of the youths and threatened to increase taxation and forced labour. This response however led to the final division of the kingdom of Israel. According to Nelson²² Rehoboam's answer devaluated the voice of the people and led to division. The 10 Northern tribes led by Jeroboam seceded from the United Kingdom while 2 tribes from the south (Judah and Benjamin) went after Rehoboam.

Lessons for Nigeria

Like ancient Israel, Nigeria is a country with multiple ethnic and tribal groups. Throughout her political history, Nigeria has been battling with ethnic and tribal differences like the ancient Israelites. It is pertinent to say that Nigerians need to learn from the history of Israel that disunity can lead to division. Nigerians should not see themselves as belonging to the North, East, South or West. They should perceive themselves as a people belonging to one nation, working towards achieving a common goal. Nigerian leaders should not allow ethnic and tribal interest to supersede national interest as we can see in the reign of Solomon, when he exploited the Northern tribes in order to develop the south. Nigerian political leaders must learn a lesson from this. One of the major reasons for Niger Delta agitations was because the income derived from the region was used to develop other regions at the detriment of the Niger Delta people. This position is corroborated by Harmona Olusegun and Folaranmi Bukola when they opine that the people of Niger-Delta are being marginalized and also suffered from land degradation and environmental pollution due to oil extraction.²³

One will observe that David and Solomon's reigns were marked with tribal chauvinism. The duo laid much emphasis on their tribes which apparently led to a revolt in the time of David and Rehoboam. "What portion have we in David... to your tent O Israel" was the cry from the north. Nigerian political leaders should avoid ethnicity, tribalism and Nepotism. Political appointments should not be lopsided. It should not be for certain regions and geopolitical zones. It should reflect federal character by spreading across all ethnic groups in the country. Solomon's reign was characterized by exploitations and oppression of the people, which eventually culminated to the division of the kingdom of Israel after his death. This is also a lesson for political leaders in Nigeria. Political leaders should be concerned about the welfare of the people they govern. They should not place unnecessary yoke on them. This can be achieved by alleviating poverty in the society, provision of jobs for the teeming population of youths, provision of good roads and electricity, and adequate provision of security of lives and properties. When all these are absent, resentment comes in and people will cry out for secession.

The sins of the kings of Israel also attribute to the division of the kingdom. For example, Solomon encouraged the worship of other gods because of his foreign wives who distracted his heart from Yahweh. It is a lesson for both citizens and rulers of Nigeria. "Righteousness exalt a nation and sin is a reproach to any people" (Psalms 14:34). For Nigeria to be united as a nation, her citizens and her rulers must do away with sin and all forms of unrighteousness. The Nigeria society today is marked by ritual killings, kidnapping, abduction, banditry, terrorism, rape and so on. On the part of political leaders, there are numerous cases of embezzlement, misallocation of public funds, political assassinations, social injustice and the violation of the rule of law etc. All these shades of sin could lead to divine wrath which may eventually lead to national calamity.

Conclusion

This paper examines the concept of national unity and its challenges to Nigeria. The paper reveals that the problem emerged from the amalgamation of the Northern and southern protectorates by the colonial administration. Most scholars agree that the amalgamation in 1914 sowed the seed of disunity in the Nigeria polity simply because since then, our political structure is based on ethnic and tribal sentiments, unequal distribution of national income, and uneven development among various ethnic groups that constitute the Federal Republic of Nigeria. In view of the above, this paper surveys the political history of Ancient Israel right from the institution of monarchy and ascertained that tribal disunity plays a pivotal role in the division of the United

Kingdom of Israel that was somehow built by David. The lessons derived from this division became the crux of the paper.

The following steps are necessary in fostering unity and national integration. Nigerians should see themselves as one political entity, irrespective of their ethnic, cultural and tribal differences. Nigerian politicians and political leaders should uphold the spirit of national unity and national integration. The concept of federal character should be strictly adhered to in the distribution of national income and resource control. Political offices should not be lopsided. Political appointments should follow the principles of equity and fairness. Developmental projects should not be concentrated on particular regions at the detrimental of others. Government should embark on sensitization programmes to orientate the citizens on the need to live in peace and harmony as one Nigeria. The Nigerian polity should be re-structured to accommodate ethnic, tribal and cultural differences. Religious leaders should take it as a matter of duty to preach love, unity and brotherhood to their members.

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